

s, COCH₃), 3.65 (2H, s, CH₂-N), 4.45 (2H, s, OCH₂) and 7.2-7.7 (8H, m, Ar-H).

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Studies on 4(3H)-Quinazolinone Derivatives as Antimalarials

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4(3H)-Quinazolinones are associated with broad spectrum biological activities¹⁻⁴. The high antimalarial activity of febrifugine⁵, an alkaloid with 3-substituted-4(3H)-quinazolinone structure, initiated the preparation and testing of several quinazolinones⁶⁻⁹ as potential antimalarials. Sengupta *et al.*¹⁰ showed that 2-mercapto-3-allyl-4(3H)-quinazolinone and its 6-methyl analogue were active antimalarials at 4 quinine equivalent of dosage¹⁰. Recently, 6-bromo-3-phenyl-2-(N,N-diethylcarbamoylmethyl)thio-4(3H)-quinazolinone and 6-bromo-3-m-chlorophenyl-2-(N,N-ethylphenylcarbamoylmethyl)thio-4(3H)-quinazolinone have been found to be active against *P. gallinaceum* in chicks¹¹. Considering these facts and that the biological activity of compounds is influenced by various substituents and their positions, a number of 2-(N,N-disubstituted-aminoethylthio)-3-alkyl/aryl-6-iodo-4(3H)-quinazolinones having the general structure 2 have been synthesised for testing their antimalarial activity.

The synthetic procedure to obtain these compounds (2) was alkylation of the sodium salt of the corresponding 2-thio-3-alkyl/aryl-6-iodo-4(3H)-quinazolinones (1) with the appropriate 2-(N-substituted or N,N-disubstituted amino)ethyl bromide hydrobromide salts¹. The intermediates (1) were synthesised by refluxing 5-iodoanthranilic acid with various alkyl/aryl-isothiocyanates. The synthesis of 4(3H)-quinazolinones (2) with 3-aryl substituents has been published elsewhere¹.

In addition, a model experiment on the benzoylation of 2-thio-3-methyl-4(3H)-quinazolinone was carried out. The product 2-benzoylthio-3-methyl-4(3H)-quinazolinone (3) when subjected to acid hydrolysis gave the corresponding sulphur free hydroxy compound 3-methyl-2,4(1H, 3H)-quinazolidione¹² (4). This shows that like alkylation^{12,13}, acylation also takes place at the sulphur atom at position-2 of the heterocyclic system. An unequivocal proof of the structure of 3 is provided by an unambiguous synthesis of its structural isomer (5) from N-benzoylanthranilic acid and methyl isothiocyanate. The two compounds 3 (m.p. 248°) and 5 (m.p. 95°) differ widely in melting point and show non-superimposable infrared spectra particularly in the fingerprint region.

In all thirteen representative compounds (no. 7 and twelve others published earlier¹) were screened for their antimalarial activity in mice infected with *P. berghei*; all of them were found to be inactive at 1 quinine equivalent of dosage. The animals were administered oral doses of 32 mg of the test compounds per kg body weight twice daily for 3 days; in untreated mice used as control parasitaemia was comparable to treated groups at the end of the treatment. The tests were carried out at the National Institute of Communicable Diseases, Delhi.

NOTES

TABLE 1—2-(*N,N*-DISUBSTITUTED-AMINOETHYLTHIO)-3-ALKYL-6-iodo-4(3*H*)-QUINAZOLINONES (2)*

Sl. no.	R	Yield %	M.p. °C	Colour	Mol. formula**	Analysis% : Found/(Calcd.)		ν_{\max} (cm ⁻¹)
						C	H	
(R ¹ = R ² = H)								
1.	OH ₂	55	319	Light yellow	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ IN ₂ OS	36.74 (36.57)	3.27 (3.32)	3 265m, 3 220w, 1 725s, 1 650s, 1 300m, 1 270m
2.	C ₂ H ₅	60	241	Yellow	C ₁₃ H ₁₄ IN ₂ OS	38.53 (38.41)	3.69 (3.73)	3 200w, 3 095m, 1 720s, 1 660s, 1 610s, 1 290s
3.	C ₆ H ₅ OH ₂	75	245	White	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ IN ₂ OS	47.03 (46.68)	3.86 (3.66)	3 195w, 3 085m, 1 710s, 1 660s, 1 610w, 1 275m
(R ¹ = R ² = C ₂ H ₅)								
4.	C ₂ H ₅	55	250	Light yellow	C ₁₅ H ₁₇ IN ₂ OS	44.65 (44.54)	4.97 (5.10)	1 720s, 1 655s, 1 615w, 1 600w, 1 290s, 825m
5.	C ₆ H ₅ OH ₂	70	251	Light brown	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ IN ₂ OS	51.15 (51.12)	4.79 (4.87)	1 720s, 1 665s, 1 620m, 1 600w, 1 280s
(R ¹ = H, R ² = OH(OH ₂) ₂)								
6.	OH ₂	60	310	Light yellow	C ₁₄ H ₁₃ IN ₂ OS	42.03 (41.69)	4.55 (4.47)	3 220m, 1 725s, 1 625s, 1 510m, 1 265m
7.	C ₂ H ₅	70	255	White	C ₁₆ H ₁₇ IN ₂ OS	42.89 (43.18)	5.04 (4.79)	3 210m, 1 720s, 1 620s, 1 520s, 1 260m
8.	C ₆ H ₅ OH ₂	65	250	Light brown	C ₂₀ H ₁₇ IN ₂ OS	49.92 (50.10)	4.64 (4.59)	3 210m, 1 725s, 1 625s, 1 500m, 1 260m
(R ¹ R ² = (OH ₂) ₂)								
9.	CH ₃	55	309	Light grey	C ₁₄ H ₂₀ IN ₂ OS	46.11 (45.75)	4.38 (4.66)	1 730s, 1 640s, 1 500w, 1 290m, 1 260m
10.	C ₆ H ₅ OH ₂	60	251	Dark red	C ₂₂ H ₁₉ IN ₂ OS	51.76 (52.08)	4.94 (4.75)	1 730s, 1 630s, 1 490m, 1 270m
(R ¹ = C ₆ H ₅ , R ² = OH ₂)								
11.	OH ₂	65	159	Light grey	C ₁₆ H ₁₅ IN ₂ OS	49.45 (49.89)	4.38 (4.16)	1 720s, 1 630s, 1 600m, 1 490m, 1 290m
12.	C ₆ H ₅ OH ₂	75	248	Dark brown	C ₂₂ H ₁₇ IN ₂ OS	54.58 (54.66)	4.24 (4.17)	1 730s, 1 645m, 1 630s, 1 615m, 1 280s

* Compounds Sl. no. 4, 8, 10 and 12 crystallised from benzene-ethanol (1 : 1), Sl. no. 2 from benzene-ethanol (2 : 1), and the rest from benzene-ethanol (3 : 1).

** Analyses for N and S were found satisfactory.

Experimental

Melting points were observed in open capillary tubes with a Gallenkamp apparatus and are uncorrected. Elemental analyses (C, H and N) were carried on a Coleman analyser. The ir spectra were recorded on Perkin-Elmer 257 and 750 grating spectrophotometers. The purity of compounds was checked by tlc using silica gel G (E. Merck).

5-Iodoanthranilic acid was prepared by a known method¹⁴. *N*-Substituted- and *N,N*-disubstituted-2-bromoethylamine hydrobromides were obtained from the corresponding 2-aminoethanols¹⁵ by reaction with 48% hydrobromic acid by adopting the literature methods^{16,17}. The following intermediates were prepared: 2-bromoethylamine hydrobromide, m.p. 170–72° (lit.¹⁶ 174°); *N,N*-diethyl-2-bromoethylamine hydrobromide, m.p. 210–12° (lit.¹⁷ 208°); 2-isopropylaminoethyl bromide hydrobromide, m.p. 129–31° (Found: C, 24.62; H, 5.70; Br, 64.41. C₈H₁₃Br₂N requires: C, 24.30; H, 5.26; Br, 64.77%), ν_{\max} (nujol) 3 250–3 500s (br, N—H

stretch) and 1570s cm⁻¹ (N—H bend); *N*-(2-bromoethyl) piperidine hydrobromide, m.p. 238° (Found: N, 4.91; Br, 58.12. C₇H₁₃Br₂N requires: N, 5.12; Br, 58.60%); 2-(*N*-phenyl-*N*-methyl)aminoethyl bromide hydrobromide, m.p. 259° (Found: C, 37.01; H, 4.63; Br, 53.82. C₉H₁₃Br₂N requires: C, 36.61; H, 4.40; Br, 54.20%).

2-Thio-3-ethyl-6-iodo-4(3*H*)-quinazolinone (1, R = C₂H₅): It was prepared by condensing 5-iodoanthranilic acid (5.26 g) with ethyl isothiocyanate (1.74 g) in absolute ethanol (35 ml) in 50% yield by the reported method¹⁸, m.p. 280° (EtOH) (Found: N, 8.30; S, 10.01. C₁₅H₁₃IN₂OS requires: N, 8.43; S, 9.68%); ν_{\max} (nujol) 3 250m, 1 720m, 1 660s, 1 600m, 1 500m and 1 260m cm⁻¹.

Similarly, 2-thio-3-methyl- and 3-benzyl-6-iodo-4(3*H*)-quinazolinones were prepared^{19,20}.

2-(β -*N*-Isopropylaminoethylthio)-3-ethyl-6-iodo-4(3*H*)-quinazolinone (2): 2-Thio-3-ethyl-6-iodo-4(3*H*)-quinazolinone (2.0 g) was dissolved in a minimum amount of 10% ethanolic sodium hydroxide

and treated with a solution of 2-isopropylaminoethyl bromide hydrobromide (1.8 g) in absolute ethanol (10 ml). The mixture was stirred and allowed to stand for 40 min. The product was filtered, washed several times with water followed by a little ethanol. It was crystallised from benzene-ethanol (3 : 1) to give dirty white needles (70%), m.p. 255° (Found : C, 42.89 ; H, 5.04 ; N, 10.13 ; S, 7.53. $C_{15}H_{20}IN_2OS$ requires : C, 43.18 ; H, 4.79 ; N, 10.07 ; S, 7.67%) ; ν_{max} (nujol) 3 210m, 1 720s, 1 620s, 1 520s, 1 260m, 825m and 760m cm^{-1} .

Similarly, other 2-(N-substituted-aminoethylthio)-3-alkyl-6-iodo-4(3H)-quinazolinones (2) were prepared. Their yields, melting points, colour of crystals, analytical data and characteristic ir bands are reported in Table 1.

2-Benzoylthio-3-methyl-4(3H)-quinazolinone (3) : A solution of 2-thio-3-methyl-4(3H)-quinazolinone^{1,2} (1.5 g) in 10% alcoholic sodium hydroxide was stirred with benzoyl chloride (1.2 g) for 5–10 min. A white precipitate was obtained which was filtered and crystallised from ethanol to yield white fibrous needles (70%), m.p. 248° (Found : C, 65.10 ; H, 4.15 ; N, 9.21 ; S, 11.12. $C_{16}H_{18}N_2O_2S$ requires : C, 64.86 ; H, 4.05 ; N, 9.46 ; S, 10.81%) ; ν_{max} (nujol) 1 685s, 1 665m, 1 640m, 1 625s, 1 545s, 1 295s, 1 170m, 1 130m, 1 090m, 1 005m, 800m, 765s and 690m cm^{-1} .

Hydrolysis of 2-benzoylthio-3-methyl-4(3H)-quinazolinone (3) : 6N Hydrochloric acid (15 ml) was added to a solution of 2-benzoylthio-3-methyl-4(3H)-quinazolinone (2.2 g) in ethanol (30 ml) and heated under reflux for 4 h. Ethanol was then distilled off and the reaction mixture poured into ice-cold water. The product obtained as white needles was filtered and dried. Recrystallisation from ethanol gave pure 3-methyl-2,4(1H,3H)-quinazolinone (4 ; 1.5 g), m.p. 244° (lit.^{1,2} 244°) ; ν_{max} (nujol) 1 690s, 1 640m, 1 625s and 1 550s cm^{-1} .

1-Benzoyl-3-methyl-2-thio-2,4(1H,3H)-quinazolinone (5) : A mixture of N-benzoylanthranilic acid (2.0 g), methyl isothiocyanate (0.6 g) and absolute ethanol (10 ml) was heated under reflux on a water-bath for 4 h. On cooling, the solid product was filtered and triturated with 5% aqueous sodium bicarbonate followed by a little aqueous ethanol. The crude material was dissolved in 10% alcoholic sodium hydroxide solution, filtered and reprecipitated by addition of dilute hydrochloric acid. The product was again triturated with water and crystallised from ethanol to give white crystals (75%), m.p. 95° (Found : C, 64.72 ; H, 4.34 ; N, 9.32 ; S, 10.56. $C_{16}H_{18}N_2O_2S$ requires : C, 64.86 ; H, 4.05 ; N, 9.46 ; S, 10.81%) ; ν_{max} (nujol) 1 690s, 1 650s, 1 610m, 1 600s, 1 540s, 1 330m, 1 280m, 1 220s, 1 185m, 1 100m, 1 090m, 1 050s, 910s, 890s, 815s, 810m, 780m, 760s, 725m, 710m and 665m cm^{-1} . The ir spectrum of 5 was non-superimposable with that of 3 in the fingerprint region.

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Synthesis and Biological Activity of Thiazolo- and Phenylthiazolo-2-carboxamido-pyrazoline and -isoxazoline Derivatives

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THIAZOLE derivatives in general are largely used as antifungal¹, antibacterial², antitumour³, anthelmintic⁴ and diuretic⁵ agents. Further, pyrazoline and isoxazoline derivatives⁶⁻⁹ have also been claimed as potential biologically active compounds. Hence, if a pyrazoline and isoxazoline moiety be